

NextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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1 Executive summary

The corporate identity of NextGEMS consists of our project logo, fonts and colors. We further created templates for report deliverables, presentations and A0 posters. Those templates shall be used by the consortium members to facilitate their day-to-day work while at the same time such templates create a recognition value of our project in dissemination activities.

2 Conclusion & Results

A survey among the project members resulted in the highest frequency of usage of the Microsoft Power Point software for designing scientific posters and presentations. We therefore developed the respective templates and use the A0 poster template to demonstrate the developed corporate identity in section 4.

3 Project objectives

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | no |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP1	Relevance in this deliverable?
Day to day project management	no
Scientific coordination including quality assurance (KPI) and risk assessment	no
Data management	no
Ensure efficient innovation management, managing exploitation of project results	no
Supporting communication and dissemination activities	yes
Clustering with EC, regional and international projects/programmes	no

Objectives of WP10	Relevance in this deliverable?
Implement, monitor and adjust an effective strategy for NextGEMS coproduction, communication & dissemination and video presence (O3)	yes
Connect model development and application communities and integrate potential users into the coproduction activities (coproduction process) (O3)	no
Develop novel communication and dissemination forms to maximize the visibility and usability of the project and its results to target audiences (communication and dissemination) (O3)	yes
Provide technical and policy briefings to the competent authorities to make them aware of project results (policy dissemination) (O3)	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1 The Project Corporate Identity

The project logo (see Fig. 1) resembles all scientific themes as well as the management structure of NextGEMS. The logo has a pink component representing the society part *Storms & Society* in the project. Continuing clockwise, the light green represents the land component *Storms & Land*, dark blue the ocean component *Storms & Ocean* and light blue the atmospheric or radiation component *Storms & Radiation*. The arrangement in a circle symbolizes the mutual interaction of the four components as well as the necessity of all components for a realistic representation of our Earth system.

4.2 Templates

Based on a poll within the NextGEMS community, the most frequently used tool for designing presentations is Microsoft Power Point and second most are GWDG pads (<https://pad.gwdg.de>). For posters, the most favourite option is again Power Point, while the second choice is LaTeX. We therefore started to create templates for presentations and posters in Power Point, the latter being used for the document shown in Figure 1. The design of the poster template is inspired by the *#betterposter* initiative by Mike Morrison [1]. The design is such that a catchy main statement shall make by-passing peers in a poster session aware of your project. The main figure(s), in our case in Figure 1 the project logo, shall additionally attract the people, while supplemental material (here the templates) are arranged at the right edge for detailed discussions that interested people will engage in.

The title slide of the Power Point presentation template is included on the lower right. The template includes similar to the poster template the project colors, font and most important, the footer with the EU flag and grant number, as well as the project logo and some space for the institute logos of the poster / presentation author(s). In addition, the report template shown on the upper right will ensure a consistent reporting of project results in all deliverables and by all consortium members. The report template is written in LaTeX as this is the most common software to produce written text in earth system science. Consortium members can use the open source online LaTeX editor Overleaf to work collaboratively on their reports.

5 References (Bibliography)

References

- [1] Mike Morrison. *Better Scientific Poster*. URL: <https://osf.io/ef53g/>. (accessed: 30.11.2021).

The project corporate identity communicates the core themes by intuitive color coding

Development of Corporate Identities and Templates

Pajam Sobhani, Theresa Mieslinger

INTRO
The installation and refinement of the projects corporate identity shall enable an intuitive presentation of the project and it's results to stakeholders.

METHODS
The corporate identity of NextGEMS consists of our project logo, fonts and colors. We further created templates for report deliverables, presentations and A0 posters.

Scan the QR code below to get to the project repository with all available templates.

RESULTS

COLOR HEX CODES

Theme colors see logo.
Supporting colors are:

- Light grey: #7E7E7E
- Dark grey: #48484B

FONT

The project font is Roboto.

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Roboto>

TEMPLATES

Project Reports

Power Point Presentation

Power Point Poster

The current document is based on the A0 portrait template

NextGEMS is funded through the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the grant agreement No - 101003470.

Take a picture to download the full poster

LATEST THINKING

Figure 1: NextGEMS A0 poster template filled with a detailed description of the project's corporate identity consisting of the project logo, font, colors, and screenshots of the project's various templates.

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

	The general public (PU)
x	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

All current as well as future templates are collected in the project internal repository. The consortium members are informed of available templates and their usage is encouraged.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 hackathon 19.10. – 22.10.2021 in Berlin

11 Full track of publications and IP

No publications so far.